

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF CADALENE *

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A new synthesis of cadalene has been described starting from *p*-methylacetophenone.

Since the isolation of cadalene from cadinenes, several syntheses of this substance have been recorded (Ruzicka and Seidel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 369; Cook and Burnett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 22; Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 536).

In the present investigation a new synthesis of cadalene has been described. *p*-Methylacetophenone has been condensed with chloroacetic ester according to Darzen (*Compt. rend.*, 1906, 142, 714) to give (I) in presence of sodium ethoxide in alcohol-petroleum ether suspension (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 2017). Hydrolysis of the glycide ester with alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide proceeds almost quantitatively with the addition of one molecule of water (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 703). When the sodium salt, thus obtained, is decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid, there is an immediate evolution of carbon dioxide with the separation of an oil. The aldehyde, thus obtained, is purified by steam-distillation, (semicarbazone, m.p. 158°). On oxidation with silver oxide the corresponding acid has also been obtained.

This aldehyde was first obtained by the interaction of chromyl chloride with cymene (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1881, v, 22, 259; *Compt. rend.*, 1880, 90, 534; cf. Paterno and Schichilone, *Gazzetta*, 1880, 10, 53). Richter and Schuchner (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1931) identified it as (*p*-tolyl)-propionaldehyde by oxidation and similar reactions. Henderson and Cameron (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 973) obtained the same aldehyde by the action of chromyl chloride on terpenene. It has already been shown by Errera (*Gazzetta*, 1889, 19, 528; 1891, 21, 76) and by Miller and Rohde (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1070; 1891, 24, 1356), that this substance is the main product of the Etard's reaction on cymene. Limonene also yields the same aldehyde under similar conditions (cf. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1871).

The aldehyde reacts with bromoacetic ester in presence of zinc according to Reformatsky to give (III). This on dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine in ether solution gives an unsaturated ester in poor yield. On distillation, the substance polymerises quickly. The most probable explanation of this appears to be the presence of the substituted phenyl group in the γ -position with respect to the carboxyl group, for the chief effect of this group is to confer an unusual degree of stability on the double

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bond in the $\alpha\beta$ -position. Attempts to prepare $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated acids by the action of bases on α -halogenated γ -phenylbutyric acids lead to unexpected results (*cf.* Linstead and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2738; Perkin and Hope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 136). Other dehydrating agents like phosphorus pentoxide in benzene solution and potassium bisulphate at 160° give similar results.

The aldehyde condenses smoothly with malonic acid in pyridine solution in presence of piperidine giving an acid (m.p. 85° - 86° , IV) in which the shifting of the double bond has taken place to the $\beta\gamma$ -position under the experimental conditions used and this explains its stability towards reducing agents like sodium amalgam. It is of interest to note that phenylacetaldehyde appears to be unique in yielding $\beta\gamma$ -acids under all conditions of condensation (Vorländer, *Annalen*, 1906, 345, 244). It is also significant to note that Rupe obtained (IV) directly by the action of magnesium methyl iodide on *p*-tolylpropionic ester, dehydration and hydrolysis taking place simultaneously (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 584). Further support in favour of its $\beta\gamma$ -structure is given by the fact that it can be converted into γ -lactone by boiling with dilute sulphuric acid and this in its turn can be reduced to (V). The saturated acid smoothly undergoes cyclisation with 85% H_2SO_4 and by the action of *isopropyl* magnesium iodide on the ketone (VI), a mixture of (VII) and the corresponding unsaturated compound results. This mixture, on selenium dehydrogenation gives cadalene (VII), identified through its picrate.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

(*p*-Tolyl)-methylglycide Ester (I).—Sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (6.5 g.) and alcohol (65 c.c.), was treated with petroleum ether (65 c.c., b.p. 90°-100°) and the mixture slowly cooled with continuous shaking, when the ethoxide was obtained in fine suspension. To this suspension, thoroughly cooled in a freezing mixture, was added with shaking, a cooled solution of *p*-methylacetophenone (34.5 g. Nellor, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 1890) and chloroacetic ester (32 g.). The mixture was allowed to rise to room temperature slowly and after standing at ordinary temperature for 16 hours, was refluxed on the water-bath for 5 hours. The dark brown solution was decomposed with ice. The upper layer was taken up in ether and repeatedly washed with ice-cold dilute potassium hydroxide solution and then with water. After the removal of solvents and unchanged materials, the fraction boiling between 130° and 145°/5 mm. was collected. On redistillation, the glycide ester boiled at 130°-35°/5 mm., yield 37.5 g. (Found: C, 70.75; H, 7.1. C₁₅H₁₆O₂ requires C, 70.9; H, 7.2 per cent).

(*p*-Tolyl)-Propionaldehyde (II).—To an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (3.7 g.) and alcohol (60 c.c.), the glycide ester (34.5 g.) was added with shaking. The mixture was cooled and to this water (3 c.c.) was added slowly with constant shaking; the mixture became hot and on continuous shaking, the whole mass became viscous and finally the crystalline sodium salt separated and the whole of the mixture solidified.

It was allowed to stand overnight. Absolute alcohol was added and the sodium salt was filtered off, washed with alcohol and ether, and next added to crushed ice and hydrochloric acid in a flask. A crystalline precipitate consisting of the free acid was perceptible for a moment. But decomposition set in immediately, an oil separating with copious evolution of carbon dioxide. The mixture was then subjected to steam distillation, the distillate extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dried (calcium chloride) and distilled. It had b. p. $92^{\circ}/6$ mm. (lit. 89° - $90^{\circ}/5$ mm.). The semicarbazone, after recrystallisation from alcohol, melted at 158° (lit. 156°). (Found: N, 20.8, 20.7. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{18}ON_3$: N, 20.5 per cent).

Ethyl γ -(p-Tolyl)- β -hydroxyvalerate (III).—A mixture of the aldehyde (17 g.), bromoacetic ester (30 g.) and zinc-wool (16 g., 2 mols.) was covered with dry benzene (75 c.c.). A crystal of iodine was added as a catalyst. On warming the mixture the reaction started and the vigour of the reaction was maintained until most of the zinc went into solution. Next it was heated for 1 hour on the water-bath. The solution was then decomposed with ice and sulphuric acid. Excess of zinc was filtered off and the benzene was thoroughly washed with ice-cold potassium hydroxide solution followed by water. From the dried (calcium chloride) solution, the hydroxy-ester was isolated by distillation, b. p. $149^{\circ}/5$ mm. as a slightly bluish fluorescent oil, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 71.35; H, 8.0. $C_{14}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 71.18; H, 8.4 per cent).

Ethyl γ -(p-Tolyl)- Δ^{β} -pentenoate.—To a well cooled solution of the hydroxy-ester (III, 21 g.) in dry pyridine (15 c.c.) and dry ether (50 c.c.), thionyl chloride (7 c.c.) was added with shaking drop by drop. The mixture was allowed to stay at room temperature for 2 hours after the addition was complete in the cold and decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was thoroughly washed with acid and alkali. The crude residue left after evaporation of ether was diluted with benzene and heated on the water-bath with precipitated copper to remove sulphur. After removal of benzene, the residue was distilled in *vacuo* when a small fraction boiled below $145^{\circ}/5$ mm. There was a continuous rise in the boiling point and finally the whole of the substance polymerised in the flask. The fraction (5 g.), isolated above, was again subjected to a further distillation and a sample was collected boiling at 134° - $36^{\circ}/6$ mm. as a mobile oil having a yellowish tinge. (Found: C, 76.9; H, 7.8. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.05; H, 8.2 per cent).

γ -(p-Tolyl)- Δ^{β} -pentenoic Acid (V).—A mixture of the aldehyde (38 g.) and malonic acid (15 g.) in pyridine (120 c.c.), and piperidine (4 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours and then on a sand-bath for 5 hours.

After decomposition with ice and sulphuric acid an oil separated which solidified to a crystalline mass. This was collected and freed from adhering oil on a porous tile, m. p. $78-81^{\circ}$, yield 30 g. After recrystallisation from petroleum ether it had m. p. $85^{\circ}-86^{\circ}$. (lit. m. p. 86°). (Found: C, 75.7; H, 7.1. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.7; H, 7.3 per cent).

1 - Keto - 4 : 7 - dimethyl - 1 : 2 : 3 : 4 - tetrahydronaphthalene (VII).— γ -(*p*-Tolyl)-valeric acid (15.5 g.), obtained by reduction of the above acid through the lactone with phosphorus and hydriodic acid, was heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with 85% H_2SO_4 (80 c.c.). The product was diluted with water after cooling and extracted with ether and the extract washed with sodium carbonate. The dried ($CaCl_2$) solution furnished the ketone, b. p. $118^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 11 g. (Found: C, 83.01; H, 8.0. $C_{12}H_{14}O$ requires C, 82.7; H, 8.0 per cent).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. $195-96^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 18.2. $C_{13}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 18.18 per cent).

Cadalene (VIII).—To magnesium isopropyl iodide prepared with magnesium (2.5 g.) and isopropyl iodide (20 g.) in ether, was added with cooling the above ketone (9 g.) in ether and the mixture allowed to stand overnight, after which the reaction was completed by heating for 3 hours and finally the mixture decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. Isolated in the usual way a mobile liquid was obtained, b. p. $119^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 7 g. It was a mixture of the hydroxy compound and its dehydration product. (Found: C, 87.3; H, 9.7. $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires C, 82.5; H, 10.1; $C_{15}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0 per cent).

The above mixture (6 g.) was heated with selenium (2 g.) for 24 hours at 300° . After cooling, the whole mass was repeatedly extracted with ether. The residue from ether was distilled in *vacuo* and the distillate redistilled over sodium when a clear mobile liquid, b. p. $106^{\circ}/3$ mm., was obtained having a characteristic aromatic smell. (Found: C, 91.5; H, 8.8. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{18}$: C, 90.9; H, 9.09 per cent).

The picrate, prepared in the usual way, crystallised in golden yellow shining needles from alcohol, m. p. $114^{\circ}-15^{\circ}$ (lit. 115°). (Found: N, 9.8. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{21}O_7N_3$: N, 9.76 per cent).

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